

D5.1 OSPO-RADAR stakeholder engagement plan

The engagement plan applies to the duration of the project; it does not include the steps that follow delivery of the final product.

A Stakeholder Engagement Plan (SEP) consists of several key components that effectively organise communication and interaction with stakeholders.

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Introduction

This document outlines the Stakeholder Engagement Plan (Deliverable D5.1) for OSPO-RADAR, part of Work Package 5. It details how Software Heritage engages stakeholders throughout the product's design, validation, and adoption. OSPO-RADAR meets a critical need: helping research institutions manage, preserve, and showcase research software in line with Open Science and existing infrastructures. This engagement plan focuses on:

- **Ensuring continuous, structured interaction** between the project team and its primary end-users (academic OSPO managers and related support roles);
- **Collecting, documenting, and integrating feedback** at key stages of the project, to inform design choices and reduce the risk of misalignment with real-world practices;
- **Providing clarity and transparency** on communication channels, decision-making processes, and responsibilities within the project team;
- **Supporting early adoption and capacity building** through training activities, documentation, and shared resources.

The scope of this plan is intentionally limited to the **duration of the OSPO-RADAR project**. It does not cover post-project dissemination, maintenance, or long-term governance of the final product, which will be addressed separately.

During the project lifespan, what does Software Heritage hope to accomplish through community engagement?

Objective	Corollary risks: What SWH wants to avoid
Keep the primary end-users continuously informed and engaged.	The primary end-user group stops interacting with the project team. Interest is lost.
Ensure the diversity of perspectives on the future final product	The end-users group includes only the usual suspects, which creates blind spots and distorts the project team's conclusions. The end-users group is for the "happy few": it's not clear how to join the discussion if you are not close enough to the SWH community.
	The primary end-user group doesn't reflect the viewpoints of future effective end-users of the products: the product is designed by managers, but will be used by others.
Ensure the purpose of the final product is understood and clear	The primary end-user group doesn't have a shared understanding of the product, who can access the product, under what conditions, and how it is deployed (e.g., centrally hosted by Software Heritage, locally installed by institutions, or offered as a hybrid model). Dissatisfaction arises from a mismatch between perceived and actual use cases.
	The SWH infrastructures partners (current and potential) don't understand the added value of the final product: how could it be integrated with their tools? Is it a threat to their own projects? The purpose and the design of the final products are not well understood. The added value of the final product is not clear to people outside of the project.

Stakeholders identification and related communication goals: Overview

Stakeholders who are out of the scope of the community project engagement plan, during the project lifespan:

- Researchers: they are secondary end-users of the future final product, as they need to track their contributions.
- Infrastructure technical managers: they ensure the consistency of the developments with the infrastructure roadmap.

Target audience	Target audience definition	Stakeholder interests and needs	Methods, Tools, and Activities for continuous information
<p>[external stakeholders] [B2C] Main end-users: Academic OSPO managers who participate in the project.</p>	<p>Individuals or organisations who will use the product. This group, drawn from academic OSPO management teams, is directly involved in product design during the project — distinct from the “Archives and Libraries” interest group.</p> <p>They are in charge, or they are involved in the OSPO organization. They have a high impact on the final product design, and they can advocate for it.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Follow up on the project progress: get detailed information - Share information about the project within their community, including the services that will be in charge of the final product integration - Make proposals and requests, describe use-cases - Ask questions - Provide feedback, test 	<p>Direct communication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - [mailing list] Provide updates on the project. Avoid information overflow and maintain engagement - [CRM] Provide support <p>Indirect communication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - [Zenodo] Public outputs can be accessed by a wider audience. - [blog] Key milestones are explained. <p>Methodological prerequisites:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organize collaborative activities (in-person, online) and prepare surveys to collect direct feedback. - Propose different types of activities during the project lifespan: sessions for small audiences, open reviews for a broad audience, etc. - Clearly state the key messaging for end-users - When possible, expand the group by making a call for volunteers by taking advantage of existing community gatherings (e.g., CURIOS monthly call) - Involve representatives from institutions located in different

Target audience	Target audience definition	Stakeholder interests and needs	Methods, Tools, and Activities for continuous information
			<p>countries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collect and curate the contacts in the CRM - Explain how to use the different channels and how to reach the team. - Within the team project, make clear who's in charge of the interactions with the end-users. - Identify when to share updates. - Use the knowledge aggregated in the helpdesk to ensure the consistency of the answers, especially for recurring questions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify recurring questions to update and improve the communication about the project
<p>[external stakeholders] [B2C] Main end-users: Academic OSPO managers who don't participate in the project, potential end-users</p>	<p>Individuals or organisations who may use the product. They don't have a direct impact on the product design at this stage. E.g., "Archives and Libraries" Interest Group members</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Follow up on the project progress: get an overview - Ask questions 	<p>Direct communication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - [CRM] Provide support. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Questions received via the ALIG mailing list should be added to the CRM. <p>Indirect communication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - [Zenodo] Public outputs can be accessed by a wider audience. - [blog] Key milestones are explained. <p>Methodological prerequisites:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify the partners who develop solutions that could be enhanced by the final product - Clearly state the key messaging for partners

Target audience	Target audience definition	Stakeholder interests and needs	Methods, Tools, and Activities for continuous information
[external stakeholders] [B2B] Secondary community partners	<p>These entities are not directly involved in the project but may be impacted by it.</p> <p>The OSPO-RADAR project could have a positive impact, for example, by expanding service offerings through new functionalities built on its final product.</p> <p>However, it may also be perceived negatively, such as by introducing competitive pressure or functional overlap with an internally planned, similar initiative. E.g., CCSD (HAL), French research software catalog team, SciCodes, etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Follow up on the project progress: get an overview, including an overview of the technical aspects - Ask questions 	<p>Direct communication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - [CRM] Provide support. <p>Indirect communication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - [Zenodo] Public outputs can be accessed by a wider audience. - [blog] Key milestones are explained. <p>Methodological prerequisites:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify the partners who develop solutions that could be enhanced by the final product - Explain how to use the different channels and how to reach the team.
[external stakeholders] [B2B] Funders	<p>Those who provide funding for the project and are interested in continuing their support in the future.</p> <p>E.g., ANR, TSA, Schmidt Sciences, Sloan Foundation, Wellcome Trust</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Follow up on the project progress: get an overview - Check the adherence to the budget - Verify the alignment between the current product development and the original scope defined in the grant proposal. 	Reports
[internal stakeholders] SWH Project team		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand project progress: milestones and calendar for organizational purposes. 	<p>Direct communication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pre-mortem work session organized at the start of the project; minutes are

Target audience	Target audience definition	Stakeholder interests and needs	Methods, Tools, and Activities for continuous information
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have a shared understanding of the priorities and reevaluate them. - Share information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - available in the SWH GitLab instance - Dedicated channel on Element. - Regular updates through team meetings. - Access to the helpdesk content. - Zotero group library to capture references. <p>Indirect communication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work documents are shared in the central internal repository. - Key messaging at disposal
[internal stakeholders] SWH team		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure a shared vision of the final product to accurately scope and mitigate risks related to its development, deployment, and maintenance. - Understand project progress: milestones and calendar for organizational purposes (e.g., task distribution within the team) - Understand how the final product will articulate in the existing architecture 	<p>Direct communication:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regular checkpoints: all-hands meetings

Stakeholder engagement checklists

Purpose: Defining success through the lens of information sharing and engagement.

The proposal is to check/assess the quality of the processes rather than relying on quantitative metrics that don't capture the work done by the project team.

	What to check?	Who's responsible within the project team?
Workshops, collaborative sessions, test sessions	<p>[Before] The organization of the event by SWH eases participation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> People know in advance what is expected of them <input type="checkbox"/> Different ways to contribute are proposed: written activities, discussions, etc. <input type="checkbox"/> The schedule may fit different time zones <input type="checkbox"/> Prerequisites are defined in advance <p><input type="checkbox"/> [Before] Different backgrounds are represented: small and large organizations Note: by the end of the project, schedule specific activities and tests for operational stakeholders, not only strategic ones. Identify a group of operational end-users, using the CRM</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> [Before] Participation is clearly credited, e.g., by asking ORCID in the roll calls, etc.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> [After] Tangible outputs were created and can be retrieved after the project by a broad audience → See "Public outputs dissemination."</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> [After] Results of the test sessions are captured in a work document</p>	<p>Workshop organizers in collaboration with the SWH Head of strategic communications</p> <p>Test sessions are led by the UX/UI expert, in collaboration with facilitators</p>
Open reviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> [Before] The feedback loop is defined in advance and described <input type="checkbox"/> [Before] There is no technical prerequisite to contribute, or if necessary, the project team offers an alternative (e.g., sending an email instead of opening an issue in a forge) <input type="checkbox"/> [After] the version that includes the proposal is disseminated alongside the original version <input type="checkbox"/> [After] The decisions that were made regarding the proposals are visible. The status (accepted, postponed, or declined) and the rationale for these decisions need to be clearly documented and communicated, especially regarding major edits (i.e., proposals or questions about the strategy). 	<p>OSPO-RADAR Project lead</p>
Talks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> [Before] Invited talks as well as answers to Calls for Papers/Contributions are listed in the CRM <input type="checkbox"/> [Before] Opportunities are chosen so that the project is presented to various audiences in terms of professional background and geographical criteria <input type="checkbox"/> [Before] Content is aligned with key messaging 	<p>OSPO-RADAR project team members who are concerned</p>

	What to check?	Who's responsible within the project team?
	<input type="checkbox"/> [After] Tangible outputs were created and can be retrieved after the project by a broad audience → See " Public outputs dissemination ."	
Helpdesk	<input type="checkbox"/> [Before] The helpdesk is being publicized to participants so that they are aware of it <input type="checkbox"/> A dispatcher regularly checks the new tickets in the CRM and assigns them <input type="checkbox"/> Requesters receive an acknowledgment of receipt <input type="checkbox"/> The answers are made using Odoo and not emails <input type="checkbox"/> The dispatcher identifies recurring questions and shares them with the project team so that concerns and proposals are identified	Helpdesk project lead
Public outputs dissemination	<input type="checkbox"/> The outputs have proper metadata and PID, using the SWH Zenodo Community <input type="checkbox"/> The outputs are promoted thanks to external comms when a significant milestone has been reached <input type="checkbox"/> The outputs are promoted via the project mailing list <input type="checkbox"/> SWH ambassadors are aware of the available resources	Engagement lead in collaboration with the SWH Head of strategic communications
Key messaging	<input type="checkbox"/> [Before] Key messaging is tested by the ambassadors (vertical Academia) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Note: Testing key messaging with the SWH team can help ensure a shared understanding of the product <input type="checkbox"/> [After] [for the project team] Key messaging exists in a formal form, accessible not only in a message. <input type="checkbox"/> [After] Key messaging is regularly shared via the project channels: e.g., mailing list. <input type="checkbox"/> [After] Key messaging is used by the project team members consistently, in particular when using the helpdesk <input type="checkbox"/> [After] The key messaging final version is shared with the SWH ambassadors.	OSPO-RADAR Project lead, in collaboration with the WP5 lead and the SWH Head of strategic communications Project members depending on their area of expertise.

	What to check?	Who's responsible within the project team?
News on the mailing list	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> The messages are sent according to a pre-defined calendar <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Is it a newsletter? No, rather wrap-ups. The sending frequency is not fixed, but based on the project milestones. <input type="checkbox"/> The content is designed to increase the engagement during the project: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Inform about the key dates and progress ○ Follow-up ("Reply section"): bug fixes, comments from the community, questions asked in the Helpdesk ○ Debunk misconceptions ○ Call for input or collaboration ○ Focus on users experiences, based on the materials gathered during tests sessions and collaborative activities 	<p>WP5 lead: is responsible for planning, writing, editing, sending</p> <p>Project team members: participate in the reviews</p>

Focus on the use of the mailing list

- Target audience: primary end-users, actively involved in the project (e.g., they participate in the tests)
 - The current mailing list is designed for public updates, for people who aren't directly involved but have an interest in the project. Internal and external lists should be kept apart, as the purpose is not the same.
- Purpose:
 - Delivering information about the project itself, and not SWH in general
 - Helping the primary end-users navigate through the channels, understand the milestones
 - Allowing the primary end-users to exchange, starting a small community of practice based on the use of the product, not OSPO topics in general

Next steps

- Key messaging:
 - Collect materials to identify the main misconceptions and/or risks to be mitigated
 - Prepare an operational framework

- Setting up the internal mailing list:
 - The tooling
 - The content strategy
- Helpdesk:
 - Internal organization
 - Public launch and external communication